

Industrious Selection: Survival of the Fittest within a Unified Growth Framework

Chi Pui Ho ¹

¹ *The University of Hong Kong, Pokfulam, Hong Kong*

Received 27 July 2023 ♦ Accepted 8 December 2023 ♦ Published 18 February 2026

Citation: Ho CP (2026) Industrious Selection: Survival of the Fittest within a Unified Growth Framework. *Population and Economics* 10(1):183-218. <https://doi.org/10.3897/popecon.10.e110161>

Abstract

We have developed a unified growth theory aimed at reconciling the various revolutions that occurred in Britain over the past millennium, including the Agricultural Revolution, Structural Transformation, Industrial Revolution, Industrious Revolution, and Demographic Revolution. A key component of our theory is the introduction of the Industrious Selection mechanism, whereby individuals with greater industriousness gradually come to dominate the population composition over time. Through a process of labor-leisure optimization and the income effect on the number of births, Industrious Selection leads to an increase in working hours, intensification of production, and acceleration of the development process. We argue that Industrious Selection is a crucial factor in understanding and explaining British development history, particularly regarding phenomena such as the rise in working days during the Malthusian era when other economic variables were in stasis.

Keywords

Industrious Selection; British Development History; Unified Growth Theory

JEL codes: N10, O50

1. Introduction

“Always there must have been, and always there must continue to be, a survival of the fittest ... Among the civilized human races, the equilibration becomes mainly direct.”

Spencer 1864, 468

“From the war of nature, from famine and death, the most exalted object which we are capable of conceiving, namely, the production of the higher animals, directly follows.”

Darwin 1872, 429

Ever since Adam Smith (1994) inquiry into the nature and causes of the wealth of nations, how to account for the historical economic development has always been at the center of the economics discipline. Unified growth theories aim to explain the transition of an economy from Malthusian stagnation, which characterizes most of human history, to one with sustainable growth, observed in developed countries since AD1800s (Galor and Weil 2000; Galor and Moav 2002).

Yet, one puzzle that the unified growth theories overlooked was the rise in working hours that occurred during the late-Malthusian era (section 3.4). Clark (2007, 181) stated that, “work hours were very high in England by 1800 ... What exactly the transition to longer work hours took place is hard to establish ... It is clear that the transition in England had largely occurred before the onset of the Industrial Revolution. But work hours in medieval England were probably already high by forager standards”. Given that most economic variables in Britain were in stasis before the eighteenth century, we hypothesize that the increase in the supply of labor hours before the eighteenth century occurred as a result of demographic selection pressure, rather than as a response to economic signals.

More specifically, this paper posits that *Industrious Selection*, a natural selection mechanism originating from humans’ optimization behavior that confers evolutionary advantages to more industrious individuals, is an integral component in reconciling the development process within a unified growth framework. We develop a unified growth theory incorporating Industrious Selection to explain how an economy transits from its Malthusian stagnating state to one with sustainable growth. This framework aims to reconcile temporally developmental revolutions during the transition process, including the Agricultural Revolution, Structural Transformation, the Industrial Revolution, the Industrious Revolution, and the Demographic Revolution (abbreviated as the ‘Five Revolutions’).

We proceed as follows:

Section 2 reviews the relevant literature.

Section 3 describes the background and historical facts related to the five revolutions.

Section 4 develops the unified growth model, wherein a distinctive feature is population heterogeneity: there are two types of individuals – one possessing the ‘industrious trait’, willing to supply more labor hours to the market than the other type. Assuming the ‘industrious trait’ is perfectly inheritable from parents to children, and through consciously working harder, the more industrious individuals earn higher incomes than the less industrious ones. Through an income effect on the number of births, the more industrious individuals gain an evolutionary advantage, gradually dominating the population composition (referred to as ‘Industrious Selection’). This results in increase in average working hours and production intensity, and facilitates the nation’s growth and development. The model also incorporates demographic-economic components and mechanisms to explain the onset of the five revolutions.

Section 5 applies the model to simulate British development process and reconcile the five revolutions.

Section 6 highlights some points for discussion.

Section 7 concludes.

2. Related literature

Our work is related to three bodies of literature.

The first set of literature pertains to unified growth theories, which explain how an economy evolves through a three-stage development process: from the Malthusian

regime, through the post-Malthusian regime, to the Modern Growth regime. The literature originated with the pioneering works of Galor and Weil (2000) and Galor and Moav (2002). Galor and Weil (2000) proposed that the inherent positive interaction between population size and technology level in the Malthusian era would accelerate technological progress, allowing a transition to the post-Malthusian era. The accelerated technological progress would, in turn, raise demand for human capital and ultimately trigger a fertility decline, leading to the onset of the Modern Growth era. Galor and Moav (2002) introduced household heterogeneity in preference related to child quality versus quantity. Households placing greater emphasis on child quality would have an evolutionary advantage during the Malthusian era. On the eve of the Industrial Revolution, the prevalence of such of households in the population would rise sufficiently to enable sustainable economic growth.

The theories have been extended along production and demography fronts. For the production side, Hansen and Prescott (2002), Doepke (2004), Strulik and Weisdorf (2008) and Lagerlöf (2010) investigated unified growth theories with dual sectors: as long as technological progress in the Solow (less land-intensive) sector is fast enough compared to the Malthus (more land-intensive) sector, an economy will eventually break through the stagnating equilibrium where per capita income growth is bounded by the land constraint. For the demography side, features such as capital complementarity to gender (Galor and Weil 1996), child mortality (Lagerlöf 2003a), life expectancy (Cervellati and Sunde 2005), gender gap (Lagerlöf 2003b), parental altruism (Soares 2005) and slavery (Ho 2022) have been added to the theories. One overlooked issue in the unified growth theories mentioned earlier is the reconciliation for the onset of the Industrious Revolution. According to De Vries (1994, 249), “The industrious revolution was a process of household-based resource reallocation that increased both the supply of marketed commodities and labor and the demand for market-supplied goods.” As mentioned in section 1, it remains a puzzle on what exactly caused the transition to longer working hours in Britain by AD1800. Considering this puzzle and the abundance of labor-leisure tradeoff theories in modern macroeconomics (Becker 1965; Kydland and Prescott 1982), it is surprising that there has been little research incorporating labor-leisure tradeoff to provide an explanation¹. We will fill this research gap (section 4).

The second body of literature is about structural transformation, which explains changes in production structures that accomplish growth and development. Kongsamut et al. (2001) proposed that, with a nonhomothetic household preference, neutral technological progress shifts production inputs away from a sector with lower income elasticity of demand through the income effect. Ngai and Pissarides (2007) posited that biased technological progress leads to sectoral shifts through the relative price effect. In Leukhina and Turnovsky (2016), population growth induces factor movements across sectors with different degrees of diminishing returns to labor. These papers assume homogenous households, and hold population growth rate exogenous to focus on different causes of structural transformation. In this paper, we relax these assumptions to examine how the above channels explain demographic-economic development within a model framework with heterogeneous population and endogenous fertility (section 5).

1 One exception is Vollrath (2009)'s work. He proposed a unified growth theory where the Industrious Revolution is a consequence of manufacturing productivity growth.

The third related body of literature, despite a bit far from the main idea of demographic selection pressure highlighted in this paper, is the institutional approach to explain economic development. North (1981, 166) explained the Industrial Revolution occurred in Britain during the late eighteenth century because of “a combination of better-specified and enforced property rights and increasingly efficient and expanding markets.” Acemoglu and Robinson (2012, Ch.7) argued that “The Industrial Revolution started and made its biggest strides in England because of her uniquely inclusive economic institutions. These in turn were built on foundations laid by the inclusive political institutions brought about by the Glorious Revolution. It was the Glorious Revolution that strengthened and rationalized property rights, improved financial markets, undermined state-sanctioned monopolies in foreign trade, and removed the barriers to the expansion of industry ... These inclusive economic institutions gave men of talent and vision such as James Watt the opportunity and incentive to develop their skills and ideas and influence the system in ways that benefited them and the nation.” Rather than presenting a competing explanation for the onset of the British Industrial Revolution, our unified growth theory emphasizes that demographic selection is an integral component in explaining the British development process. This is especially evident in the rise in working hours at the dawn of the Industrial Revolution, acting as an accelerator for the development process.

3. Historical evidence

To provide background information on the developmental revolutions our model aims to reconcile, this section presents historical evidence related to the five revolutions during the British development process².

3.1. Agricultural Revolution

The timing of the Agricultural Revolution in Britain remains a much-debated topic. Earlier views among economic historians dated the British Agricultural Revolution to the late-eighteenth and early-nineteenth centuries (Toynbee 1894, 27; Ernle 1936, 149; Overton 1996, 206), arguing for rapid growth in land and labor productivity, coinciding with the British Industrial Revolution. In recent decades, revisionist historians have contested this, asserting that the majority of agricultural productivity growth occurred by the mid-eighteenth century (Jones 1965; Kerridge 1967, 15; Allen 1999). For example, Allen (2004, 116) stated that, British “agriculture had already revolutionised itself between 1600 and 1750 ... In that period, yields, output and labour productivity all increased sharply ... The agricultural revolution did not run concurrently with the industrial revolution but rather preceded it”.

Figure 1 depicts Allen (2000)’s estimates of agricultural output per worker in England during AD1300-AD1800, and Figure 2 depicts Clark (2002)’s estimates of agricultural productivity in England during AD1500-AD1912. In general, agricultural productivity rose from AD1600 onwards, and came to a halt during the late-eighteenth century, and resumed its growth in the nineteenth century.

² Britain is chosen among many developed countries because of the rich sources of historical data and estimates available. It was also the first industrializing country; Mokyr (1999, 127) dubbed it the “Holy Land of Industrialism”.

Figure 1. Agricultural output per worker (1500 = 1.00), England, AD1300-AD1800. *Source:* Allen (2000) Table 8.

Figure 2. Agricultural productivity index (1860 = 100), England, AD1500-AD1912. *Source:* Clark (2002) Table 5.

3.2. Structural Transformation

This paper focuses on one aspect of structural transformation: the redistribution of labor hours from agricultural to manufacturing sectors. Figure 3 depicts Broadberry et al. (2013) and Clark (2010, 2013a)’s estimates of agricultural labor share in England during AD1381-AD1861. Broadberry et al. demonstrated that the shift from agriculture to manufacturing began in Britain during the sixteenth century, whereas Clark’s findings suggested that this transition occurred primarily after the seventeenth century.

Figure 3. Agricultural labor share, England, AD1381-AD1861. Note: Agricultural labor share, England, AD1381-AD1861. Solid (blue) line: Broadberry et al. (2013) estimates. Dotted (red) line: Clark (2010, 2013a) estimates. Sources: Broadberry et al. (2013) Table 9; Clark (2013a) Table 2, section 7 for AD1381-AD1660 data; Clark (2010) for AD1680-AD1851 data.

3.3. Industrial Revolution

The date of British Industrial Revolution is commonly set between AD1760 and AD1830 (Ashton 1948)³. The period marked “For the first time in history, the living standards of masses of ordinary people have begun to undergo sustained growth” (Lucas 2002, 109). While the magnitude of the rise in living standard is still being debated, the optimistic and pessimistic parties both agreed that the real wages showed sustainable increases by the AD1820s (Lindert and Williamson 1983; Feinstein 1998; Clark 2005). Figure 4 depicts Feinstein (1998) and Clark (2005)’s real wages estimates during AD1760-AD1870, with the indices being set to 100 in AD1860, to illustrate the above point. From Clark (2010)’s estimates, average per capita income growth rate was 0.29% per annum in AD1760-AD1830.

An essential aspect of the Industrial Revolution is the decisive rise in the rate of productivity growth which facilitated for sustainable per capita income growth⁴. Figure 5 depicts Clark (2010)’s per capita income (solid line) and total factor productivity (dashed line) estimates in England spanning from AD1200 to AD2000. “The upturn in productivity growth rates can be located to the 1780s/1790s”, where such growth rates “increased from close to zero to close to 1% per year ... within 50 years of 1800 in England” (Clark 2014a, 217, 220).

3 AD1769 was a hallmark year for British industrialization. In that year three important machines were invented: the Spinning Jenny by James Hargreaves, the Water Frame by Richard Arkwright and the Steam Engine by James Watt.

4 Before the AD1980s, economic historians tended to consider the British Industrial Revolution as a widespread phenomenon and the overall productivity growth rate was high (Feinstein 1981; McCloskey 1981). Crafts (1985), Crafts and Harley (1992), Harley (1999) made downward adjustments to the overall productivity growth rates and argued that the productivity growth was confined to some key manufacturing sectors and agriculture only. See Mokyr (1999) and Clark (2014a) for surveys on the British Industrial Revolution.

Figure 4. Real wages (1860=100), England, AD1760-AD1870. Sources: Feinstein (1998) Appendix Table 1, Average Full-Employment Real Earnings. Clark (2005) Table A2, Craftsmen’s Real Wage.

Figure 5. Per capita income (1860 = 100) and Total factor productivity (1860 = 100), England, AD1200-AD2000. Notes: Dotted (red) line: Total factor productivity (1860=100), England, AD1200-AD2000. Sources: Clark (2010) Tables 28, 33-34.

What was the engine of such productivity growth? North (1981, 162) stated that “learning by doing can explain the technology developed during the Industrial Revolution”. Similarly, Crafts (1995, 761) stated that during the British Industrial Revolution, “Arrow-like learning by doing was much more important relative to intentional, profit-seeking R&D than in today’s world”.

3.4. Industrious Revolution

De Vries (2008, x) placed the Industrious Revolution between AD1650 and AD1850. An important aspect of the Industrious Revolution was the augmentation in the (average) supply of labor hours (section 2). Figure 6 depicts Allen and Weisdorf (2011)'s annual working days per person estimates in Britain from AD1433 to AD1870, and De Vries (2008)'s estimates of female labor-force participation rates in the United Kingdom from AD1955 to AD1999. Both variables demonstrated a general upward trend within their respective timeframes, thereby contributing to the increase in labor hours supply.

Figure 6. Annual working days, Britain, AD1433-AD1870/Female labor-force participation rates in U.K., AD1955-AD1999. *Note:* Solid (blue) line: Annual working days, Britain, AD1433-AD1870. Dashed (red) line: Female labor-force participation rates in U.K., AD1955-AD1999. *Sources:* annual working days from Allen and Weisdorf (2011) Table 2; female labor-force participation rate from De Vries (2008) Table 6.1.

Given that most economic variables in Britain remained in stasis before the eighteenth century, we hypothesize that the increase in labor hours supply before the eighteenth century occurred as a result of Industrious Selection (demographic selection pressure against the less industrious individuals), rather than as a response to economic signals. Subsequent increases were primarily a reaction to the significant wage increase following the Industrial Revolution.

3.5. Demographic Revolution

Fertility rates declined in Britain during the nineteenth century. Figure 7 depicts the gross reproduction rate and net reproduction rate in England and Wales from AD1541 to AD2008.⁵ British fertility started its long-run decline in around AD1820.

In the current literature, there are at least five explanations for the fertility decline: a decline in mortality (Notestein 1976), increase in relative child cost (Lindert 1980), an increase in female wage (Becker 1991, 140), the child quality-quantity tradeoff (Becker and Lewis 1973), and the old-age security hypothesis (Caldwell 1976). The increase-in-relative-child-

⁵ Gross reproduction rate is defined as the average number of daughters that would be born to a woman. Net reproduction rate is defined as the average number of daughters that would be born to a woman and survive through her childbearing years.

cost channel is significant in explaining the British fertility decline during the early-nineteenth century. A crucial aspect of child cost is food prices, the “ultimate check to population” (Malthus 1826, 12)⁶. Figure 8 depicts Broadberry et al. (2011)’s estimated price of agriculture goods relative to industry goods in Britain from AD1270 to AD1870. In the early-nineteenth century, there was a notable surge in the relative agricultural price. We hypothesize that this increase elevated the relative cost of raising children, thereby triggering the Demographic Revolution.

Figure 7. Gross reproduction rate and Net reproduction rate, England and Wales, AD1541-AD2008. *Source:* Wrigley et al. (1997) Table A9.1 for AD1541-AD1866 data (solid lines). Office of National Statistics for AD1941-AD2008 data (dotted lines).

Figure 8. Relative agricultural price, Britain, AD1270-AD1870. *Source:* Broadberry et al. (2011) Agriculture price index divided by Industry price index.

⁶ Malthus (1826, 12) stated that, “[t]he ultimate check to population appears then to be a want of food, arising necessarily from the different ratios according to which population and food increase.”

We refute the notion of mortality decline as a cause of the fertility decline in the AD 1820s. Figure 9 depicts Chesnais (1992)'s estimates of crude birth rate (solid line) and crude death rate (dashed line) in England and Wales from AD 1735 to AD 1984⁷. Before the AD 1820s, fertility and mortality generally exhibited opposite trends, which undermines mortality decline as a significant factor contributing to the fertility decline.

Figure 9. Crude birth rate and Crude death rate, England and Wales, AD1735-AD1984. *Source:* Chesnais (1992), Appendix 1 for CBR, Appendix 3 for CDR.

We also disregard child education investment and the resulting quality-quantity tradeoff as key factors responsible for the British fertility decline in the early-nineteenth century (Galor and Weil 2000; Lagerlof 2006). Figure 10 depicts Flora et al. (1983)'s estimates of percentage of children aged 5 to 14 who enrolled in primary school in England and Wales from AD1855 to AD1914. Although data for periods before AD 1855 are unavailable, we speculate that the enrollment rate remained below 10% throughout the first half of the nineteenth century. Therefore, increasing education investment was likely not the primary cause of the British fertility decline in the AD1820s.

4. The Model

Consider a closed overlapping generation economy extending over infinite discrete time periods, indexed by t .⁸ Households exhibit heterogeneity, with some being more hardworking and valuing leisure less. This trait is labeled as the “industrious trait” and is perfectly

⁷ Crude birth rate is defined as the number of births per 1,000 population. Crude death rate is defined as the number of deaths per 1,000 population.

⁸ Our model is an extension of Strulik and Weisdorf (2008)'s one, by allowing for household heterogeneity and labor-leisure tradeoff. We choose Strulik and Weisdorf (2008)'s model because it is the simplest unified growth model that we can use to demonstrate Industrious Selection and the onset of five revolutions.

Figure 10. Percentage of 5-14 age group in public primary schools, England and Wales, AD1855-AD1914. *Source:* Flora et al. (1983, 624-625).

inherited across generations. The economy comprises two sectors: agriculture and manufacturing. The agricultural sector produces food for child-rearing, while the manufacturing sector produces goods for adult consumption.

4.1. Households

There are two types of identical households in the economy. Households are indexed by i , where $i = 1$ represents the “more industrious individuals”, who possess the “industrious trait”, and $i = 2$ represents the “less industrious individuals”, who do not possess the “industrious trait”. Let L_t^1 and L_t^2 be their respective adult population size at time t .

Households in this economy live for two consecutive time periods: childhood and adulthood. Each child has one parent, and we assume that a child inherits the same type (or “industrious trait”) as the parent, implying perfect inheritability of this trait from parent to child. However, it’s worth noting that this assumption raises questions about whether the “industrious trait” is translated exactly biologically, or if it could be influenced by factors such as education and informal institutions like religion. Clark’s (2007, 120) study on the wills of men in pre-industrial England revealed a significant correlation between the wealth of fathers and that of their sons. Even when sons received only a small share of their fathers’ wealth due to the presence of many surviving children, the trend persisted. This finding suggests that the primary advantages being transmitted from fathers to sons were likely either cultural or genetic in nature. And the transmission mechanism through education or informal institutions is believed to play a limited role. Regression analysis led Clark (2008, 186) to conclude that “in pre-industrial England economic success was highly heritable, and that this was mainly because the children of the rich differed genetically or culturally from the general population”. We hypothesize that traits like the “industrious trait” could represent such “highly heritable” genetic or cultural differences among different segments

of the population. Furthermore, Clark (2013b, 2014b) argued that genetics, particularly the biological inheritance of abilities, is the primary determinant of social position and economic success.

Consider a generation- t household. In childhood (time $t - 1$), a child does not work and earns no income. The child consumes one unit of food which is provided by the parent. In adulthood (time t), an adult is endowed with one unit of time, which is allocated between leisure and market work. The adult then spends the market wage income on manufacturing goods and child-rearing food. For simplicity, we assume that adults have no demand for food.

The preference of a type- i , generation- t household is defined over consumption of manufacturing goods m_t^i , leisure l_t^i and number of children n_t^i during adulthood. It is represented by the utility function:

$$u_t^i = \frac{(m_t^i)^{1-\sigma}}{1-\sigma} + \varphi_i \log l_t^i + \gamma \log n_t^i; \quad \sigma \in (0, 1), \quad \varphi_2 > \varphi_1 \geq 0, \quad \gamma > 0, \quad i = 1, 2. \quad (1).$$

The two types of households differ in the utility weight φ_i they attach to leisure: the more industrious individuals value less for leisure enjoyment, $\varphi_2 > \varphi_1 \geq 0$. The utility function features the “hierarchy of needs” (Strulik and Weisdorf 2008; Vollrath 2009): the parameter restriction $\sigma < 1$ ensures that the elasticity of marginal utility with respect to manufacturing goods is smaller than that with respect to number of children⁹. Intuitively, with such restrictions, the marginal utility from consuming more manufacturing goods diminishes at a slower rate than the marginal utility from having more children does. Consequently, as households become wealthier, they tend to allocate a higher fraction of their income towards purchasing manufacturing goods¹⁰. On the other hand, the parameter restriction $\sigma > 0$ ensures diminishing marginal utility from manufacturing goods consumption.

Continuing the choice problem for the type- i , generation- t household, in childhood the household makes no choice, but just eats and survives. In adulthood the household faces a budget constraint. If the household supplies an amount of $(1 - l_t^i)$ working hours to the market, it earns a wage income of $(1 - l_t^i)w_t$, where w_t is the wage per working hour at time t . The wage income is then divided between purchasing manufacturing goods and child-rearing food. Make the price of manufacturing goods the numéraire for all time periods, and

9 From (1), marginal utility with respect to manufacturing goods m_t^i equals $(m_t^i)^{-\sigma}$. Elasticity of marginal utility

with respect to manufacturing goods equals $\left| \frac{m_t^i}{(m_t^i)^{-\sigma}} \cdot \frac{\partial (m_t^i)^{-\sigma}}{\partial m_t^i} \right| = \sigma < 1$. Similarly, elasticity of marginal utility with respect to number of children equals 1.

10 Using later equations/results (2) and (4), for a type- i , generation- t household, fraction of income spent

on food equals $\frac{p_t n_t^i}{m_t^i + p_t n_t^i} = \frac{\gamma (m_t^i)^\sigma}{m_t^i + \gamma (m_t^i)^\sigma} = \frac{\gamma}{(m_t^i)^{1-\sigma} + \gamma}$, which is decreasing in m_t^i , if and only if $\sigma < 1$.

Therefore, we restrict $\sigma < 1$ in (1) to match Engel’s law (on individual level), which states that a household would spend a lesser fraction of income on food as income rises. Note that we have used a result that manufacturing goods consumption increases with income. See Appendix 2 mechanism 1 for the proof.

let p_t be the price of food relative to manufacturing goods at time t . Hence m_t^i and $p_t n_t^i$ are the expenditure spent on manufacturing goods and child-rearing food at time t respectively. Formally, the budget constraint facing the type- i , generation- t household in adulthood is:

$$m_t^i + p_t n_t^i = (1 - l_t^i) w_t; \quad i = 1, 2. \tag{2}$$

This type- i , generation- t household maximizes the utility function (1) subject to the budget constraint (2). This is a concave programming problem subject to a convex budget set and an interior solution is guaranteed. The optimal decisions concerning the amount of manufacturing goods to consume m_t^i , leisure l_t^i and number of births n_t^i are related by the following two equations:

$$l_t^i = \frac{\varphi_i (m_t^i)^\sigma}{w_t}; \quad i = 1, 2, \tag{3}$$

$$n_t^i = \frac{\gamma (m_t^i)^\sigma}{p_t}; \quad i = 1, 2. \tag{4}$$

In equilibrium, more industrious individuals will supply more hours to market work and earn higher wage incomes compared to less industrious individuals. Since both manufacturing goods and children are considered normal goods, more industrious individuals will consume more manufacturing goods and have more children as well. These are summarized in the following proposition:

Proposition 1 (Household maximization)

For $\sigma > 0, \varphi_2 > \varphi_1 \geq 0, \gamma > 0 \rightarrow m_t^1 > m_t^2, n_t^1 > n_t^2$, and $l_t^1 < l_t^2$ for all t .

Proof: See Appendix 1. Note from (3) and (4) that both types of households will reduce their leisure enjoyment when market wage rises. Also, they both give less birth when relative food price increases.

4.2. Demographic dynamics and Industrious Selection

Adult populations of the two types of individuals evolve according to:

$$L_{t+1}^1 = n_t^1 L_t^1, \text{ and} \tag{5}$$

$$L_{t+1}^2 = n_t^2 L_t^2, \tag{6}$$

where the initial adult populations of the two types of individuals, L_1^1 and L_1^2 , are taken as given. The total adult population and the gross population growth rate are defined as:

$$L_t \equiv L_t^1 + L_t^2, \text{ and} \tag{7}$$

$$1 + g_t^{pop} \equiv \frac{L_{t+1} + L_{t+1} n_{t+1}}{L_t + L_t n_t}. \tag{8}$$

Note that $L_t n_t$ represents the number of children in the economy at time t .

The aggregate working hours supplied by households H_t are the sum of working hours supplied by the two types of individuals:

$$H_t = (1 - l_t^1) L_t^1 + (1 - l_t^2) L_t^2. \quad (9)$$

The average leisure and average fertility rate are the population-weighted averages of their counterparts from the two types of individuals:

$$l_t = \frac{L_t^1 l_t^1 + L_t^2 l_t^2}{L_t}, \quad (10)$$

$$n_t = \frac{L_t^1 n_t^1 + L_t^2 n_t^2}{L_t}. \quad (11)$$

The above two equations, together with proposition 1, imply that, *ceteris paribus*, when the proportion of more industrious individuals (type 1) in population rises, average leisure decreases and average fertility rate increases.

From proposition 1 and population evolution equations (5)-(7), we have the following corollary:

Corollary 1 (Industrious Selection): More industrious individuals (type 1) have an evolutionary advantage in terms of population composition, that is, $\frac{L_t^1}{L_t}$ is increasing over time.

Proof: See Appendix 1.

Corollary 1 states our important result of *Industrious Selection*: when individual preferences are characterized by the “hierarchy of needs” utility function (1) with $\sigma > 0$, through labor-leisure optimization, more industrious individuals will earn higher incomes; through income effect on number of births and perfect inheritability of “industrious trait”, more industrious individuals will possess an evolutionary advantage and gradually dominate the population composition¹¹. Our theory yields a similar prediction as Darwin (1958, 120), wherein he posited that, “favourable variations would tend to be preserved, and unfavourable ones to be destroyed” in the struggle for life. Here, Industrious Selection suggests that a specific variation of the human species, characterized by more industrious individuals, is destined to survive in the long run¹². However, it is humans’ conscious maximization activity, instead of “struggle for existence in relation to other organic beings or to external conditions” (Darwin 1872, 69), that underlies natural selection in our model. The fittest of the human species is defined by fecundity, the ability to consciously raise the largest num-

11 The prediction from Corollary 1 contrasts with Galor and Moav (2002). In their paper, population heterogeneity originates from individuals possessing different preference on child quality versus child quantity – “high quality” type attaches a higher utility weight to child quality than “high quantity” type does. Galor and Moav (2002) showed that, the “high quality” type has an evolutionary advantage over the “high quantity” type during the Malthusian era, and such an advantage is reversed after the Malthusian pressure relaxes. Their model predicts that the “high quantity” type will dominate the population composition in the long run. In contrast, in our model, the more industrious individuals always have an evolutionary advantage over the less industrious ones, and they will dominate the population composition in the long run.

12 Clark (2007, 166) stated the emergence of “Modern Man” during the long Malthusian era: “Work hours rose ... societies [became] increasingly middle class in their orientation. Thrift, prudence, negotiation, and hard work were becoming values for communities that previously had been spendthrift, impulsive, violent, and leisure loving”. In our theory, the “Modern Man” will be more industrious than the primitive man.

ber of offspring. This opens up an additional channel of evolution in human society when compared to the animal kingdom.^{13,14}

4.3. Production

In the economy, there are two sectors responsible for producing final output: the agricultural (food) sector and the manufacturing sector. Labor hours serve as the sole input in both sectors. Agricultural production is characterized by diminishing returns to labor hours, meaning that as more labor is applied to agricultural production, the additional output generated per unit of labor decreases. Additionally, learning-by-doing serves as the sole engine of technological progress in both sectors (Arrow 1962; Matsuyama 1992) (section 3.3)¹⁵.

4.3.1. The Agricultural sector

Agricultural output at time t , Y_t^A , is given by:

$$Y_t^A = \mu (A_t)^\varepsilon (H_t^A)^\alpha ; \mu > 0, \varepsilon \in (0,1), \alpha \in (0,1), \tag{12}$$

where H_t^A is labor hours employed by the agricultural sector at time t , $A_t > 0$ is the endogenously determined agricultural productivity at time t . The assumption $\alpha \in (0,1)$ assures that agricultural production displays diminishing returns to labor hours.

Technological progress in the agricultural sector arises from learning-by-doing externality:

$$A_{t+1} - A_t = Y_t^A = \mu (A_t)^\varepsilon (H_t^A)^\alpha, \tag{13}$$

where A_1 is taken as given.

Here, we assume that the agricultural technological progress has a simple one-to-one relationship with the level of agricultural output. The parameter restriction $\varepsilon \in (0,1)$ entails diminishing returns to learning-by-doing in the agricultural sector.

The growth rate of agricultural productivity at time t is:

$$g_t^A \equiv \frac{A_{t+1} - A_t}{A_t}. \tag{14}$$

4.3.2. The Manufacturing sector

We adopt similar production and technological progress formulations in the manufacturing sector. Manufacturing output at time t , Y_t^M , is given by:

13 See Herbert Spencer's quote ahead of the Introduction. Relatedly, Becker (1991, 136-137) stated that Darwin's theory loses relevance in human society if we do not take into account parents' conscious investment to increase representation of their children in the next generation. In Galor and Moav (2002), households consciously maximize their utility subject to a survival (subsistence consumption) constraint, which generates evolutionary pressure against individuals owing child quantity-biased preferences in the Malthusian era.

14 We are aware of the potential conscious states in non-human animals (Boly et al. 2013). However, even this is the case, the channel through which conscious maximization activity generates evolutionary advantage through income effect on number of births is unique to humans.

15 As our focus is to explain the onset of the five revolutions over the AD years rather than to explain growth today, we overpass R&D, and indeed focus on learning-by-doing as the sole engine of technological progress in this paper. R&D is an important ingredient to the study of modern economic growth. See Acemoglu (2009) and Aghion and Howitt (2009) for textbook treatments.

$$Y_t^M = \delta (M_t)^\phi H_t^M; \delta > 0, \phi \in (0,1), \quad (15)$$

where H_t^M is the labor hours employed by the manufacturing sector at time t , M_t is the endogenously determined manufacturing productivity at time t . Note that manufacturing production does not display diminishing returns to labor hours.

Technological progress in the manufacturing sector is again fueled by learning-by-doing externality:

$$M_{t+1} - M_t = Y_t^M = \delta (M_t)^\phi H_t^M, \quad (16)$$

where M_1 is taken as given.

There are diminishing returns to learning in the manufacturing sector ($\phi < 1$).

The growth rate of manufacturing productivity at time t is:

$$g_t^M \equiv \frac{M_{t+1} - M_t}{M_t}. \quad (17)$$

Equations (13) and (16) show that population affects production and growth through the scale effect – a larger aggregate labor hours supply implies that either labor hours employed in the agricultural sector (H_t^A), or that in the manufacturing sector (H_t^M) increase. This will intensify production and speed up productivity growth in at least one of the sectors.

4.3.3. The Aggregate final output

The aggregate final output at time t , Y_t , is given by the sum of values of agricultural output at time t , $p_t Y_t^A$, and of manufacturing output at time t , Y_t^M :

$$Y_t = p_t Y_t^A + Y_t^M. \quad (18)$$

Note that the price of manufacturing output is the numéraire in the economy, and p_t is the relative food price at time t .

Per capita income at time t , y_t , is given by:

$$y_t = \frac{Y_t}{L_t + L_t n_t}. \quad (19)$$

Per capita income growth rate at time t , g_t^y , is defined as:

$$g_t^y \equiv \frac{y_{t+1} - y_t}{y_t}. \quad (20)$$

4.4. Market clearing and wage equalization

To close our model, we impose three conditions.

4.4.1. Labor market clearing

The first condition is labor market clearing. At each time t , the total labor hours employed by the two production sectors equal the aggregate working hours supplied by households:

$$H_t^A + H_t^M = H_t. \quad (21)$$

Following the approaches in classical growth models and unified growth models (Solow 1956; Galor and Weil 2000; Galor and Moav 2002; Strulik and Weisdorf 2008) we adopt the “full employment” condition. This condition posits that every household can work as much

as they desire to maximize utility, subject to their time constraint. However, it's important to note the limitation of such an assumption, as highlighted by Solow (1988). The model, under this assumption, may not account for short-run deviations from the equilibrium growth path.

4.4.2. Food market clearing

The second condition is food market clearing. At each time t , the demand for food (for child-rearing purpose) equals the supply of food from the agricultural sector, meaning $n_t L_t = \mu(A_t)^\epsilon (H_t^A)^\alpha$. We define θ_t to be the fraction of the economy's working hours devoted to agricultural production (agricultural labor hours share) at time t . Manipulating the food market equilibrium condition gives:

$$\theta_t \equiv \frac{H_t^A}{H_t} = \frac{1}{1-l_t} \left[\frac{(L_t)^{1-\alpha} n_t}{\mu(A_t)^\epsilon} \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} \tag{22}$$

Agricultural labor hours share increases with the population size, average fertility rate and average leisure; it decreases with the agricultural productivity level.

Similarly, we define χ_t to be the fraction of the economy's working hours devoted to manufacturing production (manufacturing labor hours share) at time t . By (21):

$$\chi_t \equiv \frac{H_t^M}{H_t} = 1 - \theta_t \tag{23}$$

Manufacturing labor hours share rises if labor hours are released from the agricultural sector.

4.4.3. Wage equalization

The third condition is wage equalization across the two production sectors. We make two assumptions: first, labor hours are completely divisible and are freely mobile across sectors. Second, labor hours are paid according to the average product in the two sectors.¹⁶ At each time t , wage equalization implies:

$$w_t = \frac{p_t Y_t^A}{H_t^A} = \frac{Y_t^M}{H_t^M} \tag{24}$$

The first equality in (24) gives the wage determination equation:

$$w_t = p_t \frac{\left[\mu(A_t)^\epsilon \right]^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}}{(n_t L_t)^{\frac{1-\alpha}{\alpha}}} \tag{25}$$

The second equality in (24) gives the food price determination equation:

$$p_t = \frac{\delta(M_t)^\phi (\theta_t L_t)^{1-\alpha}}{\mu(A_t)^\epsilon} \tag{26}$$

¹⁶ This is a type of "share economy" (Drazen and Eckstein 1988, 437), where production incomes are divided among the working force.

Note that by Walras' law, when all other markets are in equilibrium, the manufacturing goods market will also attain its equilibrium: $Y_t^M = L_t^1 m_t^1 + L_t^2 m_t^2$.

4.5. Equilibrium price and quantities

The first period of our model is indexed with $t = 1$, and the relevant initial conditions for the economy are given by $\{L_1^1, L_1^2, A_1, M_1\}$. The equilibrium for the economy constitutes sequences of household allocation $\{m_t^1, m_t^2, l_t^1, l_t^2, n_t^1, n_t^2\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$, production variables $\{Y_t^A, Y_t^M, Y_t, y_t\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$, sectoral productivities $\{A_{t+1}, M_{t+1}\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$, population variables $\{L_t, L_{t+1}^1, L_{t+1}^2, H_t, l_t, n_t\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$, sectoral inputs $\{H_t^A, H_t^M\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$, sectoral labor hours shares $\{\theta_t, \chi_t\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$, prices $\{w_t, p_t\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$, and growth rates $\{g_t^y, g_t^{pop}, g_t^A, g_t^M\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$, which satisfy:

(A) Household utility maximization: Given prices, $\{m_t^i, l_t^i, n_t^i\}$ maximize household utility function (1) subject to budget constraint (2) for both types $i = 1, 2$ at time t .

(B) Output production: Given technology levels, labor hours input in each sector at time t , sectoral outputs $\{Y_t^A, Y_t^M\}$ are obtained by the sectoral production functions (12) and (15). The final output $\{Y_t\}$ is aggregated by (18), given prices. Per capita income $\{y_t\}$ is obtained from (19).

(C) Market clearing conditions: (21) for labor hours; (22) for agricultural goods.

(D) Wage equalization condition: Labor hours move across agricultural and manufacturing sectors until the average product of labor hours in the two sectors are equalized by (24).

(E) Sectoral labor hours share definitions: (22) and (23).

(F) Population evolution: Population size and composition $\{L_t, L_{t+1}^1, L_{t+1}^2\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$ evolve according to (7), (5), (6), while aggregate working hours, average leisure and average fertility rate $\{H_t, l_t, n_t\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$ evolve according to (9), (10), (11).

(G) Agricultural and manufacturing productivities $\{A_{t+1}, M_{t+1}\}_{t=1}^{\infty}$ evolve according to (13) and (16).

(H) Growth rate definitions: (20) for per capita income growth rate, (8) for population growth rate, (14) and (17) for agricultural and manufacturing productivity growth rates.

5. Simulation: Onset of Five Revolutions

5.1. Benchmark simulation

In this section, we investigate the long-run development dynamics implied by the model. Specifically, we utilize simulation to qualitatively illustrate the transition of Britain from its Malthusian state, through the endogenous occurrence of the five revolutions, to the Modern Growth state. We consider a model economy that spans from AD1000 to AD2200. Each model period corresponds to 20 years, approximately the length of one generation.

Table 1 shows the numerical values of benchmark parameters and initial conditions. We follow Strulik and Weisdorf (2008) in setting $\alpha = 0.8$, $\varepsilon = 0.45$, $\phi = 0.3$, $\mu = 0.5$, $\delta = 1.5$ and $\gamma = 3.4$. We let $\sigma = 0.01$ to approximate quasi-linear utility function. We let $L_1^1 = L_1^2 = 0.001$ at AD1000. We let $A_1 = 4.55$, $M_1 = 50$, $\varphi_1 = 0.7$, $\varphi_2 = 1.5$ so that the model would simulate the Industrial Revolution at AD1780. Specifically, the simulated annualized per capita income growth rate $\left(\frac{y_t - y_{t-1}}{y_{t-1}}\right)$ at AD1780 would be 0.29%, same as Clark (2010)'s estimate average per capita income growth rate of 0.29% per annum in AD1760-AD1830 (section 3.3). Also the model would simulate the maximum point of the number of children per household (n_t) to occur at AD1820, same as the timing of Demographic Revolution from Wrigley et al. (1997)'s net reproduction rate estimates (section 3.5). To compare the simulation performance against the historical data, in Britain, as mentioned above our model simulates the annualized per capita income growth in AD1780 to be same as Clark (2010)'s estimate average per capita income growth rate of 0.29% per annum in AD1760-AD1830 (section 3.3). For fertility, our model simulates the number of children per household (n_t) to be 1.28 at the onset of Demographic Revolution in AD1820, close to the average net reproduction rate of 1.57 during AD1821-AD1836 from Wrigley et al. (1997)'s net reproduction rate estimates (section 3.5). For average working hours, our model simulates that average working hours ($1 - l_t$) to increase by 6.4% during the late-Malthusian era from AD1680 to AD1800, same as the increase of 6.4% of average working days from De Vries (2008)'s estimates during AD1685-AD1800 (section 3.4).

Table 1. Benchmark parameter values, to explain the Five Revolutions

	Interpretation	Value
<i>Parameters</i>		
φ_1	Utility weight attached to leisure for type 1 individuals	0.7
φ_2	Utility weight attached to leisure for type 2 individuals	1.5
γ	Utility weight attached to number of children	3.4
σ	Elasticity of marginal utility with respect to m_t^i	0.01
μ	Agricultural production function parameter	0.5
ε	Diminishing returns to agricultural learning-by-doing	0.45
α	Diminishing returns to labor hours in agricultural production	0.8
δ	Manufacturing production function parameter	1.5
ϕ	Diminishing returns to manufacturing learning-by-doing	0.3
<i>Initial values</i>		
L_1^1	Initial adult population of type 1 individuals	0.001
L_1^2	Initial adult population of type 2 individuals	0.001
A_1	Initial agricultural technology level	4.55
M_1	Initial manufacturing technology level	50

Figure 11 (solid lines) depicts the benchmark simulated development paths for (a) log of per capita income $\log y_t$; (b) average fertility rate n_t ; (c) growth rate of agricultural productivity g_t^A ; (d) growth rate of manufacturing productivity g_t^M ; (e) average working hours $(1 - l_t)$; (f) agricultural labor hours share θ_t ; (g) relative food price p_t ; and (h) proportion of the more industrious individuals in population L_t^1 / L_t . Panels (a)-(c), (e)-(f) aim to display the five revolutions, while the others aid our explanation. From panels (a) and (b), the per capita income and population growth paths are consistent with the three-stage development process highlighted by Galor and Weil (2000) and Galor and Moav (2002)¹⁷.

The economy experienced the Malthusian era from AD1000 to AD1780, characterized by stagnant per capita income and gradual population growth. Following this, it transitioned through the post-Malthusian era from AD1780 to AD1820, during which per capita income growth and population growth accelerated. From AD1820 onwards, the economy entered the Modern Growth era, marked by sustainable per capita income growth and a declining population growth rate.

5.2. Stasis during Malthusian era

Based on Figure 11 (solid lines), we can provide an account of the British development process. Throughout the High Middle Ages to the early Modern Period (AD1000-AD1600), the economy remained in a state of stasis, characterized by constant levels of most economic and demographic variables. This stasis was primarily due to the low starting levels of population, agricultural and manufacturing productivities, resulting in small sectoral outputs and slow learning-by-doing (panels (c)-(d)). The growth in population dissipated the slow overall productivity growth, thereby confining per capita income at a low level (panel (a)). During this period, production was concentrated in the agricultural sector to meet the food demand (panel (f)), fostering relatively faster technological progress in agriculture. However, gradual population growth continuously raised food demand, preventing a significant drop in relative food prices (panel (g)).

The stability of the relative food price, which represents the relative cost of child-rearing, kept fertility and population growth rates at modest levels as well (panel (b)). However, one aspect that continued to change during the long Malthusian era was the population composition. According to Corollary 1, due to Industrious Selection, less industrious individuals were relatively removed from the population (panel (h)), leading to continuously increasing average working hours within this epoch (panel (e))¹⁸.

5.3. Agricultural Revolution and Structural Transformation in late-Malthusian era

During the late-Malthusian era (AD1600-AD1780), Britain witnessed the unfolding of the *Agricultural Revolution*. Thanks to population growth, Industrious Selection, and the sectoral concentration in agriculture in earlier periods, the population size and the proportion

¹⁷ In the simulation, population growth rate follows qualitatively the same growth paths as average fertility rate.

¹⁸ Clark and Hamilton (2006) found that, during pre-industrial times, the richest testators left twice as many number of children as the poorest ones did in England. Their result is consistent with our theoretical prediction that the richer ones (the more industrious individuals) would be the more fertile ones in the economy.

Figure 11. Development dynamics and the Five Revolutions, Britain, AD1000-AD2200. *Note:* Solid (blue) lines: the benchmark economy. Dashed (red) lines: the counterfactual economy, $\varphi_1 = 1.5$, otherwise benchmark parameters from Table 1. Panels (a) to (f) show log of per capita income, average fertility rate, growth rate of agricultural productivity, growth rate of manufacturing productivity, average working hours, agricultural labor hours share, relative food price, and proportion of the more industrious individuals in population.

of more industrious individuals in the population, as well as the agricultural technology base, had accumulated to high enough levels. Through learning-by-doing, agricultural technological progress accelerated (panel (c)), breaking through stasis and causing a drop in the relative food price (panel (g)). This reduction in the relative cost of child-rearing led to an increase in fertility (panel (b)). However, since most of the agricultural productivity growth translated into increases in the population growth rate, per capita income remained at its

low Malthusian level (panel (a)), consistent with the “Iron Law of Wages” (Ricardo 1821)¹⁹. On the other hand, agricultural productivity was high enough to sustain the population during this era, leading to *Structural Transformation* (equation (22)), wherein labor hours shifted to the manufacturing sector (panel (f)). However, manufacturing productivity growth remained slow (panel (d)).

5.4. Industrial Revolution and continuing Structural Transformation in post-Malthusian era

Next, Britain entered the post-Malthusian era (AD1780-AD1820), marked by its Industrial Revolution and the takeoff of per capita income. To facilitate our explanation, we highlight four internal adjustment mechanisms in the model²⁰:

- **[Mechanism 1: Income effect]**. Ceteris paribus, when wages increase, individual households tend to increase the number of births and consumption of manufacturing goods, as well as the portion of income spent on the latter. This increase in relative aggregate demand for manufacturing goods leads to a shift of labor hours from the agricultural sector (which produces goods with a higher elasticity of marginal utility) to the manufacturing sector (which produces goods with a lower elasticity of marginal utility)²¹.
- **[Mechanism 2: Relative price effect]**. Ceteris paribus, if the relative food price decreases, households tend to have more births. This leads to a shift of labor hours from the manufacturing sector (which experiences a relative price increase) to the agricultural sector (which experiences a relative price decrease).
- **[Mechanism 3: Technology growth effect]**. Ceteris paribus, agricultural technological progress shifts labor hours towards the agricultural sector, while manufacturing technological progress does the opposite.
- **[Mechanism 4: Population growth effect]**. Ceteris paribus, an increase in aggregate labor hours supply will shift labor hours from the agricultural sector (sector with stronger diminishing returns to labor hours) to the manufacturing sector (sector with weaker diminishing returns to labor hours).

To summarize the four mechanisms: a wage increase and a relative food price drop will raise fertility; a wage increase, manufacturing productivity growth, and aggregate labor hours (or population) growth will shift working hours to the manufacturing sector; a relative food price drop and agricultural productivity growth will shift working hours to the agricultural sector. Ceteris paribus, these adjustments occur due to the complex interplay of income effects, relative price effects, technological growth effects, and the supply of aggregate labor hours in the economy.

19 Ricardo (1821, 87-88) stated that the reproductive response of labor to real wage changes would in turn keep real wage at around the long-run natural level: “It is when the market price of labour exceeds its natural price, that the condition of the labourer is flourishing and happy, that he has it in his power to command a greater proportion of the necessaries and enjoyments of life, and therefore to rear a healthy and numerous family. When, however, by the encouragement which high wages give to the increase of population, the number of labourers is increased, wages again fall to their natural price, and indeed from a re-action sometimes fall below it.”

20 See Appendix 2 for mathematical proofs and explanations of the four mechanisms.

21 In our model, the direction of labor hours shift caused by the income effect is theoretically ambiguous. To be more precise, with a heterogeneous population, although Engel’s law always holds on the individual level, it does not necessarily hold on the aggregate level. This is a more general result than Kongsamut et al. (2001)’s model with a homogeneous population. Numerically, given our parameter values and initial conditions, the simulation result shows that the income effect always induces an agricultural-to-manufacturing structural transformation throughout the British development process. See Appendix 2 Mechanism 2 for more details.

During the post-Malthusian era, Structural Transformation facilitated the takeoff of manufacturing technological progress (panel (d)), which in turn slowed down the pace of the relative food price decline (panel (g)). As a result, the rate of fertility increase decelerated (panel (b)), driven by the slower drop in the relative cost of child-rearing. With this deceleration in fertility, some improvement in aggregate productivity could translate into an increase in per capita income rather than a proportional increase in population. This pivotal moment marked Britain's breakaway from the Malthusian Trap (panel (a)), signaling the onset of the *Industrial Revolution*. It's worth noting that the real wage, although not shown in Figure 11, also experienced a significant increase during this period.²² The wage improvement, coupled with manufacturing technological progress and population expansion, accelerated the shift of labor hours from the agricultural to the manufacturing sector (Mechanisms 1, 3, 4) (panel (f)). This led to a mass production of manufacturing goods in Britain.²³ The wage takeoff also increased the opportunity cost of leisure for households, prompting both types of households to supply more labor hours to the market, thus initiating the *Industrious Revolution* (panel (e)). As a result, households shifted their consumption from leisure to market-supplied goods. Furthermore, through learning-by-doing, the structural transformation and increase in aggregate labor hours supply further accelerated manufacturing technological progress, creating virtuous cycles of wage growth, structural transformation, labor hours supply increase, and manufacturing productivity growth.

5.5. Demographic Revolution and continuing Structural Transformation in Modern Growth era

In AD1820, the *Demographic Revolution* began as the average fertility rate declined (panel (b)), marking Britain's entry into the Modern Growth era. This revolution was triggered by the "ultimate check to population" (Malthus 1826): a rise in the relative food price (panel (g)). Since the late-Malthusian era, the shift of labor hours towards manufacturing (panel (f)) had led to enhanced learning-by-doing in the manufacturing sector (panel (d)). The relatively mass production of manufacturing goods eventually pushed up the relative food price, reversing the previously observed relative price effect [Mechanism 2] and the fertility trend in AD1820.²⁴

During the Modern Growth era (after AD1820), the continuous decline in fertility added momentum to the previously mentioned virtuous cycles.²⁵ This decline further bolstered per capita income and wage growth. In terms of structural transformation, the relative price effect now pushed labor hours towards the manufacturing sector. Additionally, the increased wage incentivized households to work more, become wealthier, and allocate increasing por-

22 In our simulation, the real wages in terms of both food price and manufacturing goods price took off in around AD1780. This result conforms to Crafts and Mills (2009)'s finding that English real wages were stationary until the end of the eighteenth century.

23 The simulated relative food price was declining before AD1820, so the relative price effect, together with agricultural technology growth effect, exerted forces to push labor hours into the agricultural sector before AD1820 [Mechanisms 2, 3].

24 Broadberry et al. (2015, 193-194) stated that, relative agricultural price rose strongly than ever before in the early-nineteenth century. The reasons were that food remained expensive while the price of manufactured goods fell dramatically due to mechanized production methods.

25 After AD1820, the faster manufacturing technological progress and agricultural-to-manufacturing labor hours shift maintained the rising trend of relative food price (panel (g)). The relative food price rise in turn lowered average fertility [Mechanism 2].

tions of their income towards manufacturing goods. This, in turn, stimulated production and learning-by-doing in the manufacturing sector. The enhanced virtuous cycles enabled Britain to achieve sustainable per capita income growth throughout the nineteenth and twentieth centuries.

5.6. Importance of Industrious Selection in unified growth theory

Incorporating Industrious Selection into our model provides an evolutionary explanation for the increase in working days before the Industrial Revolution (Figure 6). Since all economic variables remain in stasis during the Malthusian epoch, it is challenging to attribute the rise in working days solely to economic signals during this period.

To demonstrate the importance of Industrious Selection in our unified growth model, we can conduct a counterfactual experiment. Figure 11 (dashed lines) depicts the simulation result by adopting all parameters and initial conditions stated in Table 1, except re-setting $\varphi_1 = 1.5$. That means, the counterfactual economy consists of only less industrious individuals.²⁶ When compared to the benchmark economy (solid lines), the population in the counterfactual economy was homogeneous, lacking evolutionary pressure. As a result, the simulated average labor hours supply remained visually constant throughout the long Malthusian era (panel (e)). This failure to explain the rise in working days during those time periods highlights the importance of Industrious Selection as an integral component in our unified growth model.²⁷

Industrious Selection also accelerates development. Figure 11 shows that the counterfactual economy experienced the Industrial Revolution and the Demographic Revolution at later times compared to the benchmark economy. This implies that the more industrious population, benefiting from an evolutionary advantage, possesses traits that are more conducive to economic growth. As the more industrious individuals gradually dominate the population, this intensifies output production and accelerates learning-by-doing. Eventually, this allows the benchmark economy to take off earlier. In other words, industrious selection acts as a built-in accelerator for the development process in our model.

6. Discussion

6.1. Human trait evolution and Economic development

Our theory emphasizes the importance of Industrious Selection in providing an evolutionary advantage to the relatively industrious population in the development process (Corollary 1). More broadly, our theory relies on the income effect on the number of births to confer an evolutionary advantage on a certain portion of the population, whose intrinsic traits will determine overall preferences or technological evolution in the economy in the long run. The evolutionary mechanism may offer insights into constructing new theories

26 If we instead adopt $\varphi_1 = \varphi_2 = 0.7$ in the counterfactual economy, the counterfactual economy would consist of the more industrious individuals only. We will get the same qualitative result that the simulated average labor hours supply stayed visually constant throughout the long Malthusian era, failing to explain the rise in working days in those time periods.

27 Yet our benchmark model cannot replicate the large increase in working hours during AD1536-AD1578 as shown in Figure 4. The increase in working hours within this time frame was likely caused by the abolishment of 49 holy days in England during AD1536, as a consequence of the Protestant Reformation (De Vries 2008, 88). The abolishment relaxed the maximum working days constraint and the households responded by supplying more labor hours to the market during the sixteenth century.

to explain the long-run decline in violence and the rise of literacy throughout human history (Clark 2007, ch. 9). Given that most economic and demographic variables remained static over the long Malthusian era, it is plausible to consider human trait evolution as the main driver behind these long-run rising and declining trends.²⁸

Industrious Selection indeed accelerates development. The critical assumption for achieving this result is that the more industrious population, enjoying an evolutionary advantage, also inherits traits that are more conducive to economic growth. In our paper, we modeled “industriousness” as one such trait. However, it’s important to note that industriousness is not the only trait that can contribute to economic growth.

For instance, those who enjoy an evolutionary advantage might also possess traits such as being better entrepreneurship innovators (Schumpeter 1934), more willing to engage in education and training (Mincer 1958), more capable to deal with disequilibria associated with economic growth (Schultz 1975), better at redesigning institutions that solve coordination failures and facilitate market integration (Epstein 2000, ch. 1), or more likely to learn and adopt new innovations (Spolaore and Wacziarg 2009), and so forth. These traits can also generate the accelerator property, leading to accelerated development in the economy.

What our theory emphasizes is the “supply side” of human trait evolution, but it’s crucial to recognize that the “demand side” may be just as significant. Geographic or political factors can incentivize the preservation of certain traits due to the rewards they offer. From a historical perspective, one such trait that might have been crucial to development during the Modern Period was the shipbuilding trait.

For instance, consider the examples of Portugal and China in the fifteenth century. For Portugal, there was a “strategic benefit in being located on the South Atlantic coast of Europe near to the exit of the Mediterranean” (Maddison 2001, 57). Indeed, the demand for Portuguese deep-sea fishing and the African slavery trade could have incentivized the Portuguese to reward the shipbuilding trait. Conversely, while China was leading the Europeans in shipbuilding techniques by the early fifteenth century, the Ming dynasty’s “increasing concern to defend the new northern capital, Beijing, against potential invasion from Mongolia or Manchuria” led it to abandon ocean diplomacy. As a result, fleets and sea-going junks were reduced or prohibited. (Maddison 2007, 163). Under these circumstances, it is not surprising that the shipbuilding trait hardly gained an evolutionary advantage in China compared to Portugal, or more generally, in the Atlantic European nations.²⁹ This might explain why Atlantic European nations dominated the oceans in the Age of Discovery, despite their inferior shipbuilding technology at the outset.³⁰

28 Our model accounts for leisure preferences and choices, yet omits the tradeoff between child quality and quantity, along with human capital investment as depicted in Galor and Moav (2002). We might also interpret our findings – that the more industrious individuals have an evolutionary advantage – as a specific case where average human capital growth is zero in the economy. For example, as we argued in section 3 that during the Demographic Revolution, human capital growth in terms of education enrollment rate was slow before AD1820s. We might interpret that during such period of essentially zero average human capital growth, the more industrious individuals possessed an evolutionary advantage in the society that drove up the average working hours in Britain during the long Malthusian era.

29 In the late-fifteenth century, the Chinese emperor ordered to retrieve the documents concerning Zheng He’s treasure voyages (AD1405-AD1433) from the War Office. However, the officer extracted the documents, and burned them, describing the contents as “deceitful exaggerations of bizarre things far removed from the testimony of people’s ears and eyes” (Duyvendak 1939, 395-396).

30 For example, Maddison (2001, 76, 92) also mentioned that the Netherlands has “occupied a flat amphibious terrain where the relationship between land and water was very close”, and that in Britain “the strategic advantages of being an island were intelligently exploited. The British merchant fleet was greatly expanded”.

6.2. Demographic shock and Survival of the Fittest

Our theory also suggests implications for the potential effect of demographic shocks on economic development. If a negative demographic shock were to relatively eliminate the population possessing traits unconducive to economic growth, the nation's development process might be accelerated. One significant demographic shock in European history that exemplifies this is the Black Death³¹ in the fourteenth century.

The Black Death (AD1346-AD1353) stands as one of the most severe epidemic outbreaks in human history. It devastated regions across Europe, North Africa, Asia Minor, and the Middle East during the mid-fourteenth century. In Europe particularly, it's estimated that between 25% and 60% of the population perished during the first few years of the outbreak³². Table 2 shows the population estimates of Britain (England and Wales) in the fourteenth century, where we observe a large depopulation after the onset of the Black Death.

Table 2. Independent estimates for population in England in the fourteenth century

Year	Population (in millions)	Source
1300	5.75	Pamuk (2007, 294)
1310	> 6	Campbell (1991, 49)
1316	6	Clark (2007, 30)
1347	3.7	Russell (1966, 16)
1348	4.81	Broadberry et al. (2011, Appendix 50)
1400	3	Pamuk (2007, 294)

The outbreak of the Black Death has been considered by some historians as “a turning point in history” (Bowsky 1971). It marked the time division between the High Middle Ages and the late-Medieval Period. Despite the immense suffering and loss of life it brought to Europe, the Black Death also catalyzed significant economic and social changes that laid the groundwork for the transition to the Modern Period. First, depopulation created labor scarcity and boosted workers' wages, shifting the balance of power from employers to employees, and from landlords to peasants (Phelps Brown and Hopkins 1956; Penn and Dyer 1990; O'Brien and Roseberry 1991, 25). Second, the plagues accelerated the changes in consumption pattern: there were dietary improvements; households shifted their consumption from food to manufacturing goods (Dyer 1988; 1998, 174-175; Voigtländer and Voth 2013a). Third, the increase in labor wages encouraged innovations in labor-saving technologies, such as the replacement of grain farming by animal husbandry, and the adoption of water mills (Gottfried 1983, 138; Barbier 2011, 199). The impact of the Black Death extended beyond economic and social realms to influence various aspects of culture, education, medical science, architecture, religion, art, and marriage patterns. (Herlihy 1997, ch.3; Ziegler 1997, ch.16-17; Voigtländer and Voth 2013b). As summarized by Benedictow

31 The Black Death was a plague pandemic that reached Europe in 1347 and spread to England in 1348.

32 Gottfried (1983, xiii) stated that, “The Black Death ... devastated the Western world from 1347 to 1351, killing 25%-50% of Europe's population and causing or accelerating marked political, economic, social, and cultural changes”. Ziegler (1997, 185) accepted that “a third of the population died of the Black Death”. Benedictow (2004, 383) estimated an average death toll of 60% in Europe between AD1346-AD1353. Over a longer time horizon, Herlihy (1997, 17) stated that European population had been reduced by about two-thirds by the AD1420s.

(2004, 393): “By creating a great deficit of labour [the Black Death] speeded up economic, technological, social and administrative modernization ... It also hastened the breakdown of feudal economic structures and mentalities and the rise of a prevailing dynamic capitalist market economy and concomitant innovative and dynamic attitudes and mentalities.”

Complementing Benedictow’s claim, from the implications of our theory, the Black Death might have triggered a sweeping change in the overall population’s quality, leading to a concept akin to “Survival of the Fittest” as societies moved towards the Modern Period. This theoretical argument relies on the assumption that the poor were more vulnerable to the Black Death than the wealthy. Benedictow (2004, 262, 266) provided two reasons why this was likely the case: “Firstly, poor people lived in far more unhygienic environments ... which increased their exposure to rat fleas; secondly, in pre-plague society, many poor and destitute people may have had their physiological resistance to disease (immunity) significantly impaired or weakened by long-term undernutrition or malnutrition”; data indicated that “the mortality among the poor and destitute was 5-6 percentage points higher than the mortality among the better-off social classes”. Similarly, Herlihy (1997, 55-56) noted that medieval observers generally agreed that the poor were “much more susceptible” to plague infection than the rich. Some even claimed that “the Black Death of 1348 wiped out the poor completely.”³³ Byrne (2012, 243, 288) also stated that: “Plague epidemics seemed to begin among the poor and to strike them the hardest ... As the 14th century produced one more plague outbreak after another, authorities came to conclude a direct correlation between poverty and the disease.”

If the poor people being wiped out by the plagues contained traits un conducive to economic growth, then the outbreak of the Black Death during the mid-fourteenth century was the “turning point in history” when the plagues accelerated the process of “Survival of the Fittest” in the European societies, leaving their population with traits more conducive to economic development, ultimately contributing to the rise of Europe relative to the other parts of the world.³⁴

7. Conclusion

This paper presents a unified growth theory with Industrious Selection to reconcile the development process that a nation undergoes. Initially, a nation experiences Malthusian stagnation due to slow technological progress being dissipated by population growth. However, through conscious labor-leisure optimization and the income effect on the number of births, individuals with greater industriousness gain an evolutionary advantage over those less industrious, gradually dominating the population composition (*Industrious Selection*). Over time, this leads to an increase in working hours and production intensity, thereby accelerating technological progress. Through learning-by-doing, concentration on agricultural production during the Malthusian era has facilitated faster productivity growth in the agricultural sector, culminating in the Agricultural Revolution. Once agricultural productivity reaches a level sufficient to sustain the population, Structural Transformation occurs, and labor hours shift to the manufacturing sector. This shift promotes technological progress

³³ The difference in mortality rates between the rich and the poor depends on how the rich and the poor were defined. But their qualitative implications are the same: the poor were more susceptible to the Black Death than the rich.

³⁴ See Charles Darwin’s quote ahead of the Introduction.

in manufacturing, slowing the decline in relative food prices and fertility rates. Ultimately, this triggers the Industrial Revolution, pulling the economy out of the Malthusian Trap. Subsequently, the nation enters the post-Malthusian era, characterized by sustainable per capita income growth. The Industrious Revolution also occurs as households respond to substantial increases in market wages by supplying more labor hours. Continuous structural transformation and rapid productivity growth in the manufacturing sector eventually lead to a decline in relative manufacturing prices. As a result, households prefer to expand their consumption of cheaper manufacturing goods rather than giving birth to children, triggering the Demographic Revolution. Subsequently, the nation enters the Modern Growth era, characterized by a long-run decline in fertility rates.

Our unified growth theory successfully simulates long-run development paths that align closely with British historical experience over the past millennium. Specifically, our simulations accurately reconcile the timings of the Industrial and Demographic Revolutions, as well as the observed increase in working hours during the Malthusian era when other economic variables remained in stasis.

Industrious Selection introduces an additional dimension to the process of natural selection in human societies, distinct from that observed in the animal world (Darwin 1872): it is not just the most adaptable humans that survive, but also the ones that are most industrious. This interaction between humans' survival and maximization activities, coupled with biological-demographic, socio-political, and economic factors, shapes past and modern economic growth in diverse landscapes. Exploring how these dynamics interact and influence economic development is an ongoing and fascinating inquiry. Future research into this issue holds the potential to enrich our understanding of the nature and causes of the wealth of nations.

References

- Acemoglu D (2009) Introduction to modern economic growth. Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- Acemoglu D, Robinson JA (2012) Why nations fail: the origins of power, prosperity, and poverty. Crown Publishers, New York.
- Aghion P, Howitt P (2009) The economics of growth. MIT Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- Allen RC (1999) Tracking the agricultural revolution in England. *The Economic history review* 52: 209–35. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-0289.00123>.
- Allen RC (2000) Economic structure and agricultural productivity in Europe, 1300–1800. *European Review of Economic History* 4: 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1361491600000125>.
- Allen RC (2004) Agriculture during the industrial revolution, 1700–1850. In: Floud R, Johnson P (Ed.) *The Cambridge Economic History of Modern Britain*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 96–116. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521820363.005>.
- Allen RC, Weisdorf JL (2011) Was there an 'industrious revolution' before the industrial revolution? An empirical exercise for England, c. 1300–1830. *The Economic history review* 64: 715–29. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0289.2010.00566.x>.
- Arrow KJ (1962) The Economic Implications of Learning by Doing. *The Review of Economic Studies* 29: 155–73. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2295952>.
- Ashton TS (1948) *The industrial revolution: 1760–1830*. Oxford university Press., London.
- Barbier E (2011) *Scarcity and frontiers: how economies have developed through natural resource exploitation*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, UK.

- Becker GS (1965) A Theory of the Allocation of Time. *The Economic journal* (London) 75: 493–517. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2228949>.
- Becker GS (1991) *A treatise on the family*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- Becker GS, Lewis HG (1973) On the Interaction between the Quantity and Quality of Children. *The Journal of political economy* 81: S279–88. <https://doi.org/10.1086/260166>.
- Benedictow OJ (2004) *The Black Death, 1346-1353: the complete history*. Boydell Press, Woodbridge, Suffolk, UK.
- Boly M, Seth AK, Wilke M, Ingmundson P, Baars B, Laureys S, Edelman DB, Tsuchiya N (2013) Consciousness in humans and non-human animals: recent advances and future directions. *Frontiers in Psychology* 4: 625. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2013.00625>.
- Bowsky WM (1971) *The Black Death: a turning point in history?* Holt, Rinehart and Winston, New York.
- Broadberry S, Campbell BMS, Klein A, Overton M, van Leeuwen B (2011) *British Economic Growth, 1270-1870: An Output-based Approach*.
- Broadberry S, Campbell BMS, Klein A, Overton M, van Leeuwen B (2015) *British economic growth, 1270-1870*. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
- Broadberry S, Campbell BMS, van Leeuwen B (2013) When did Britain industrialise? The sectoral distribution of the labour force and labour productivity in Britain, 1381–1851. *Explorations in Economic History* 50: 16–27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eeh.2012.08.004>.
- Byrne JP (2012) *Encyclopedia of the Black Death*. ABC-CLIO, Santa Barbara, Calif.
- Caldwell JC (1976) Toward A Restatement of Demographic Transition Theory. *Population and development review* 2: 321–66. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1971615>.
- Campbell BMS (1991) *Before the Black Death: studies in the 'crisis' of the early fourteenth century*. Manchester University Press, Manchester.
- Cervellati M, Sunde U (2005) Human Capital Formation, Life Expectancy, and the Process of Development. *American Economic Review* 95: 1653–72. <https://doi.org/10.1257/000282805775014380>.
- Chesnais JC (1992) *The demographic transition: stages, patterns, and economic implications: a longitudinal study of sixty-seven countries covering the period 1720-1984*. Clarendon Press, Oxford.
- Clark G (2002) *The Agricultural Revolution and the Industrial Revolution: England, 1500-1912*.
- Clark G (2005) The Condition of the Working Class in England, 1209–2004. *The Journal of political economy* 113: 1307–40. <https://doi.org/10.1086/498123>.
- Clark G (2007) *A farewell to alms: a brief economic history of the world*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, New Jersey.
- Clark G (2008) In defense of the Malthusian interpretation of history. *European review of economic history* 12: 175–99. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1361491608002220>.
- Clark G (2010) The macroeconomic aggregates for England, 1209–2008. *Research in economic history* 27: 51–140. [https://doi.org/10.1108/S0363-3268\(2010\)0000027004](https://doi.org/10.1108/S0363-3268(2010)0000027004).
- Clark G (2013a) 1381 and the Malthus delusion. *Explorations in Economic History* 50: 4–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eeh.2012.08.005>.
- Clark G (2013b) *Surnames and a Theory of Social Mobility*. University of California, Davis.
- Clark G (2014a) The Industrial Revolution. In: Aghion P, Durlauf SN (Ed.) *Handbook of economic growth*. North-Holland, an imprint of Elsevier, Oxford, 217–62.
- Clark G (2014b) *The Son Also Rises: Surnames and the History of Social Mobility*. Princeton: Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- Clark G, Hamilton G (2006) Survival of the Richest: The Malthusian Mechanism in Pre-Industrial England. *J Econ Hist* 66: 707–36. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022050706000301>.

- Crafts NFR (1985) *British economic growth during the Industrial Revolution*. Clarendon Press, Oxford.
- Crafts NFR (1995) Exogenous or Endogenous Growth? The Industrial Revolution Reconsidered. *J Eco History* 55: 745–72. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022050700042145>.
- Crafts NFR, Harley CK (1992) Output growth and the British industrial revolution: a restatement of the Crafts-Harley view. *The Economic history review* 45: 703–30. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0289.1992.tb01313.x>.
- Crafts NFR, Mills TC (2009) From Malthus to Solow: How did the Malthusian economy really evolve? *Journal of Macroeconomics* 31: 68–93. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmacro.2007.08.007>.
- Darwin C (1872) *Origin of species by means of natural selection, or the preservation of favoured races in the struggle of life*. John Murray, London.
- Darwin C (1958) *The autobiography of Charles Darwin, 1809-1882: with original omissions restored*. Collins, London.
- De Vries J (1994) The Industrial Revolution and the Industrious Revolution. *J Eco History* 54: 249–270. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022050700014467>.
- De Vries J (2008) *The industrious revolution consumer behavior and the household economy, 1650 to the present*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Doepke M (2004) Accounting for Fertility Decline During the Transition to Growth. *Journal of Economic Growth* 9: 347–83. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:JOEG.0000038935.84627.e4>.
- Drazen A, Eckstein Z (1988) On the organization of rural markets and the process of economic development. *The American Economic Review* 78: 431–43.
- Duyvendak JJJ (1939) The True Dates of the Chinese Maritime Expeditions in the Early Fifteenth Century. *T'oung pao* 34: 341–413.
- Dyer C (1988) Changes in Diet in the Late Middle Ages: The Case of Harvest Workers. *Agricultural history review* 36: 21–37.
- Dyer C (1998) *Standards of living in the later Middle Ages: social change in England, c. 1200-1520*. Cambridge University Press, New York.
- Epstein SR (2000) *Freedom and growth: the rise of states and markets in Europe, 1300-1750*. Routledge, London.
- Ernlé REP (1936) *English farming past and present*. Longmans, Green & Co., London.
- Feinstein CH (1981) Capital accumulation and the Industrial Revolution. In: Floud R, McCloskey DN (Ed.) *The Economic history of Britain since 1700*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 128–42.
- Feinstein CH (1998) Pessimism Perpetuated: Real Wages and the Standard of Living in Britain during and after the Industrial Revolution. *J Eco History* 58: 625–58. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022050700021100>.
- Flora P, Alber J, Eichenberg R, Kohl J, Kraus F, Pfenning W, Seeböhm K (1983) *State, economy, and society in Western Europe, 1815-1975: a data handbook in two volumes*. St. James Press, Chicago.
- Galor O, Moav O (2002) Natural selection and the origin of economic growth. *Quarterly Journal of Economics* 117: 1133–91.
- Galor O, Weil DN (1996) The Gender Gap, Fertility, and Growth. *The American Economic Review* 86: 374–87.
- Galor O, Weil DN (2000) Population, technology, and growth: From malthusian stagnation to the demographic transition and beyond. *The American Economic Review* 90: 806–28.
- Gottfried RS (1983) *The Black Death: natural and human disaster in medieval Europe*. Collier Macmillan, New York.
- Hansen GD, Prescott EC (2002) Malthus to Solow. *The American Economic Review* 92: 1205–17.

- Harley CK (1999) Reassessing the Industrial Revolution: A Macro View. In: Mokyr J (Ed.) *The British industrial revolution: an economic perspective*. Westview Press, Boulder, Colo., 160–205.
- Herlihy D (1997) *The black death and the transformation of the west*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- Ho CP (2022) Reconciling Reversal of Fortune in early United States Development within a Unified Growth Framework. *Annals of Economics and Finance* 23-2, 329-371.
- Ho CP (2024) Towards a more complete theory of structural transformation. *Annals of Economics and Finance* 25-1, 289-326.
- Jones EL (1965) Agriculture and Economic Growth in England, 1660-1750: Agricultural Change. *The Journal of Economic History* 25: 1–18.
- Kerridge E (1967) *The agricultural revolution*. Allen & Unwin, London.
- Kongsamut P, Rebelo S, Xie D (2001) Beyond Balanced Growth. *The Review of Economic Studies* 68: 869–82. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-937X.00193>.
- Kydland FE, Prescott EC (1982) Time to Build and Aggregate Fluctuations. *Econometrica* 50: 1345–1370. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1913386>.
- Lagerlof N-P (2003a) From Malthus to Modern Growth: Can Epidemics Explain the Three Regimes? *International economic review (Philadelphia)* 44: 755–77. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2354.t01-1-00088>.
- Lagerlof N-P (2003b) Gender Equality and Long-Run Growth. *Journal of Economic Growth* 8: 403–26. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1026256917489>.
- Lagerlof N-P (2006) The Galor–Weil model revisited: A quantitative exercise. *Review of economic dynamics* 9: 116–42. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.red.2005.07.002>.
- Lagerlöf N-P (2010) From Malthusian war to Solovian peace. *Review of Economic Dynamics* 13: 616–36. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.red.2009.10.008>.
- Leukhina O, Turnovsky S (2016) Population Size Effects in the Structural Development of England. *American Economic Journal Macroeconomics* 8: 195–229. <https://doi.org/10.1257/mac.20140032>.
- Lindert PH (1980) Child Costs and Economic Development. In: Easterlin RA (Ed.) *Population and economic change in developing countries*. University of Chicago Press, Chicago.
- Lindert PH, Williamson JG (1983) English Workers' Living Standards during the Industrial Revolution: A New Look. *The Economic history review* 36: 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2598895>.
- Lucas RE (2002) *The Industrial Revolution: Past and Future*. In: Lucas RE (Ed.) *Lectures on economic growth*. Harvard University Press, Cambridge, Mass.
- Maddison A (2001) *The world economy: a millennial perspective*. OECD Publishing, Paris, France.
- Maddison A (2007) *Contours of the world economy, 1-2030 AD: essays in macro-economic history*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.
- Malthus TR (1826) *An essay on the principle of population*. John Murray, London.
- Matsuyama K (1992) Agricultural Productivity, Comparative Advantage, and Economic Growth. *Journal of Economic Theory* 58: 317–34.
- McCloskey DN (1981) The Industrial Revolution 1780-1860. In: Floud R, McCloskey DN (Ed.) *The Economic history of Britain since 1700*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 103–27.
- Mincer J (1958) Investment in Human Capital and Personal Income Distribution. *The Journal of political economy* 66: 281–302. <https://doi.org/10.1086/258055>.
- Mokyr J (1999) Editor's Introduction. In: Mokyr J (Ed.) *The British industrial revolution: an economic perspective*. Westview Press, Boulder, Colo., 1–127.
- Ngai LR, Pissarides CA (2007) Structural Change in a Multisector Model of Growth. *The American Economic Review* 97: 429–43. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.97.1.429>.
- North DC (1981) *Structure and change in economic history*. Norton, New York.

- Notestein FW (1976) Population – The Long View. In: Schultz TW (Ed.) Food for the world. Arno Press, New York, 36–57.
- O'Brien J, Roseberry W (1991) Golden ages, dark ages: imagining the past in anthropology and history. University of California Press, Berkeley. <http://www.ons.gov.uk> [Accessed on 01.04.16].
- Overton M (1996) Agricultural revolution in England: the transformation of the agrarian economy 1500-1850. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Pamuk S (2007) The Black Death and the origins of the 'Great Divergence' across Europe, 1300-1600. *European Review of Economic History* 11: 289–317.
- Penn SAC, Dyer C (1990) Wages and earnings in late medieval England: evidence from the enforcement of the labour laws. *The Economic history review* 43: 356–76. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0289.1990.tb00535.x>.
- Phelps Brown EH, Hopkins SV (1956) Seven Centuries of the Prices of Consumables, Compared with Builders' Wage-Rates. *Economica* (London) 23: 296–314. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2551457>.
- Ricardo D (1821) On the principles of political economy and taxation. John Murray, London.
- Russell JC (1966) The Preplague Population of England. *J Br Stud* 5: 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.1086/385516>.
- Schultz TW (1975) The Value of the Ability to Deal with Disequilibria. *Journal of economic literature* 13: 827–46.
- Schumpeter JA (1934) The theory of economic development: an inquiry into profits, capital, credit, interest, and the business cycle. Harvard University, Cambridge.
- Smith A (1994) An inquiry into the nature and causes of the wealth of nations. Modern Library, New York.
- Soares RR (2005) Mortality Reductions, Educational Attainment, and Fertility Choice. *American Economic Review* 95: 580–601. <https://doi.org/10.1257/0002828054201486>.
- Solow RM (1956) A contribution to the theory of economic growth. *The quarterly journal of economics* 70: 65–94. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1884513>.
- Solow RM (1988) Growth Theory and After. *The American Economic Review* 78: 307–17.
- Spencer H (1864) The principles of biology. Williams and Norgate, London.
- Spolaore E, Wacziarg R (2009) The Diffusion of Development. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics* 124: 469–529. <https://doi.org/10.1162/qjec.2009.124.2.469>.
- Strulik H, Weisdorf J (2008) Population, food, and knowledge: a simple unified growth theory. *Journal of Economic Growth* 13: 195–216. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-008-9033-7>.
- Toynbee A (1894) Lectures on the industrial revolution of the 18th century in England: popular addresses, notes, and other fragments. Longmans, London.
- Voigtländer N, Voth H-J (2013a) The Three Horsemen of Riches: Plague, War, and Urbanization in Early Modern Europe. *The Review of Economic Studies* 80: 774–811.
- Voigtländer N, Voth H-J (2013b) How the West "Invented" Fertility Restriction. *American Economic Review* 103: 2227–64. <https://doi.org/10.1257/aer.103.6.2227>.
- Vollrath D (2009) The Dual Economy in Long-Run Development. *Journal of Economic Growth* 14: 287–312. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10887-009-9045-y>.
- Wrigley EA, Davies RS, Oeppen JE, Schofield RS (1997) English population history from family reconstitution, 1580-1837. Cambridge University Press, New York.
- Ziegler P (1997) The black death. Sutton Pub., Stroud, Gloucestershire.

Acknowledges

The author acknowledges Professor Yulei Luo, Joseph S.K. Wu, Stephen Y.W. Chiu, Chenggang Xu, Chi-Wa Yuen, Paul S.H. Lau, Fang Yang, Oded Galor, and two anonymous referees for their helpful comments, as well as seminar participants at the University of Hong Kong. Financial support from the Hong Kong PhD Fellowship Scheme (PF11-08043) and Sir Edward Youde Memorial Fellowships (for Postgraduate Research Students 2013/14) are gratefully acknowledged. The author declares that he has no conflict of interest.

Information about the author

- Chi Pui Ho. Lecturer, Faculty of Business and Economics, The University of Hong Kong, Pokfulam, Hong Kong. Email: chipuiho@hku.hk

Appendix 1

Proofs

Proposition 1

Proof: From the households' problems we have for $i = 1, 2$

$$\left(m_t^i\right)^{-\sigma}\left(w_t-m_t^i\right)-\varphi_i-\gamma=0. \tag{A.1}$$

Let the optimality condition be described as implicit function

$$F\left(m_t^i, \varphi_i\right)=w_t\left(m_t^i\right)^{-\sigma}-\left(m_t^i\right)^{1-\sigma}-\varphi-\gamma=0$$

Then, by implicit function theorem, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial m_t^i}{\partial \varphi_i} &= -\frac{F_{\varphi}}{F_m} = -\frac{-1}{-\sigma w_t\left(m_t^i\right)^{-\sigma-1}-\left(1-\sigma\right)\left(m_t^i\right)^{-\sigma}} = \\ &= -\frac{1}{\sigma w_t\left(m_t^i\right)^{-\sigma-1}+\left(1-\sigma\right)\left(m_t^i\right)^{-\sigma}} < 0. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1

Proof:
$$\frac{L_{t+1}^1}{L_{t+1}^2} = \frac{n_t^1 L_t^1}{n_t^1 L_t^1 + n_t^2 L_t^2} = \frac{L_t^1}{L_t^1 + \frac{n_t^2}{n_t^1} L_t^2} > \frac{L_t^1}{L_t^1 + L_t^2} = \frac{L_t^1}{L_t^2}.$$

The first equality follows from (5), (6) and (7). The third inequality follows from proposition 1 that $n_t^1 > n_t^2$.

Appendix 2

Adjustment mechanisms in the model

[Mechanism 1: Income effect]³⁵

Mechanism: $w_t \uparrow \rightarrow n_t \uparrow \rightarrow m_t \uparrow, l_t ? (\downarrow), \theta_t ? (\downarrow)$

Explanation: the mechanism operates through the household optimization channel. Both the number of children and manufacturing goods are considered normal goods in households' utility functions. When the relative food price is held constant, an increase in wages will relax households' budget constraints, prompting them to allocate more spending towards both goods.

It's important to note that while Engel's law (where the proportion of income spent on food decreases as income rises) holds on the individual level, it may not necessarily hold on the aggregate level.

Proof: Consider an increase in w_t , by (A.1) from Appendix 1 we have:

$$\frac{\partial m_t^i}{\partial w_t} = \frac{1}{(\gamma + \varphi_i) \sigma (m_t^i)^{\sigma-1} + 1} > 0, \quad i = 1, 2.$$

Hence $m_t \equiv \frac{L_t^1 m_t^1 + L_t^2 m_t^2}{L_t}$ also increases.

Using (2), (4), for a type- i , generation- t household, fraction of income spent on food equals $\frac{p_t n_t^i}{m_t^i + p_t n_t^i} = \frac{\gamma (m_t^i)^\sigma}{m_t^i + \gamma (m_t^i)^\sigma} = \frac{\gamma}{(m_t^i)^{1-\sigma} + \gamma}$, which is decreasing in m_t^i if and only if

$\sigma < 1$. Since we have proved above that an increase in w_t raises m_t^i , the fraction of income spent on food for this household also decreases with wage (Engel's law on individual level).

Holding p_t constant, by (4) n_t^i moves in the same direction as m_t^i and increases. Therefore

$n_t \equiv \frac{L_t^1 n_t^1 + L_t^2 n_t^2}{L_t}$ also increases. By (3)

$$\frac{\partial l_t^i}{\partial w_t} = \left[\frac{\sigma \varphi_i (m_t^i)^{\sigma-1}}{w_t \left[(\gamma + \varphi_i) \sigma (m_t^i)^{\sigma-1} + 1 \right]} - \frac{\varphi_i (m_t^i)^\sigma}{(w_t)^2} \right]$$

with sign indeterminate. From our simulation in section 5, this sign was found to be always negative in Britain throughout AD1000-AD2200. Hence an increase in w_t will cause fall in l_t^i for all i , as well as decrease in l_t .

³⁵ To be more precise, in our model with heterogeneous households, mechanism 1 should be called the "wage effect" instead of the "income effect".

By goods market equilibrium conditions and (4):

$$\frac{Y_t^M}{p_t Y_t^A} = \frac{L_t^1 m_t^1 + L_t^2 m_t^2}{p_t (L_t^1 n_t^1 + L_t^2 n_t^2)} = \frac{L_t^1 m_t^1 + L_t^2 m_t^2}{\gamma \left[L_t^1 (m_t^1)^\sigma + L_t^2 (m_t^2)^\sigma \right]}$$

Taking total derivative of the above expression with respect to w_t :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \left(\frac{Y_t^M}{p_t Y_t^A} \right)}{\partial w_t} &= \frac{\partial \left(\frac{Y_t^M}{p_t Y_t^A} \right)}{\partial m_t^1} \frac{\partial m_t^1}{\partial w_t} + \frac{\partial \left(\frac{Y_t^M}{p_t Y_t^A} \right)}{\partial m_t^2} \frac{\partial m_t^2}{\partial w_t} = \\ &= \frac{\left[L_t^1 (m_t^1)^\sigma + L_t^2 (m_t^2)^\sigma \right]^{-2}}{\gamma \left[(\gamma + \varphi_1) \sigma (m_t^1)^{\sigma-1} + 1 \right]} \left\{ \left[L_t^1 (m_t^1)^\sigma + L_t^2 (m_t^2)^\sigma \right] L_t^1 - (L_t^1 m_t^1 + L_t^2 m_t^2) \sigma (m_t^1)^{\sigma-1} L_t^1 \right\} + \\ &+ \frac{\left[L_t^1 (m_t^1)^\sigma + L_t^2 (m_t^2)^\sigma \right]^{-2}}{\gamma \left[(\gamma + \varphi_2) \sigma (m_t^2)^{\sigma-1} + 1 \right]} \left\{ \left[L_t^1 (m_t^1)^\sigma + L_t^2 (m_t^2)^\sigma \right] L_t^2 - (L_t^1 m_t^1 + L_t^2 m_t^2) \sigma (m_t^2)^{\sigma-1} L_t^2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

with sign indeterminate. From our simulation in section 5, this sign was found to be always positive in Britain throughout AD1000-AD2200. Since $\frac{Y_t^M}{p_t Y_t^A} = \frac{\delta (M_t)^\phi (1 - \theta_t) H_t}{\mu (A_t)^\varepsilon [\theta_t H_t]^\alpha}$, holding p_t, A_t, M_t, H_t constant, an increase in w_t reduces θ_t (Engel's law on aggregate level).

[Mechanism 2: Relative price effect]

Mechanism: $p_t \downarrow \Rightarrow n_t \uparrow, m_t$ constant, l_t constant, $\theta_t \uparrow$

Explanation: the mechanism operates through the household optimization channel. A decrease in relative food prices reduces the cost of child-rearing. Assuming wages remain constant, households will allocate the additional purchasing power towards raising more children³⁶. This increased demand for children necessitates a greater share of agricultural labor hours to meet the higher food demand.

Proof: Holding w_t constant, when p_t decreases, by (A.1) m_t^i stayed constant for all i .

By (4) n_t^i increases for all i . It follows immediately that $n_t \equiv \frac{L_t^1 n_t^1 + L_t^2 n_t^2}{L_t}$ increases and

$m_t \equiv \frac{L_t^1 m_t^1 + L_t^2 m_t^2}{L_t}$ remains constant. By (3) l_t^i also remains constant for all i and so does l_t .

From goods market equilibrium conditions $Y_t^A = n_t L_t$ and $Y_t^M = m_t L_t$, $\frac{Y_t^A}{Y_t^M}$ increases.

Holding A_t, M_t, H_t constant, from (12) and (15) θ_t increases.

36 A relative food price drop has no effect on individual household's manufacturing goods consumption in our model. The reason is that the substitution effect on manufacturing goods consumption is exactly offset by a relaxation on the household's budget constraint.

[Mechanism 3: Technology growth effect]

Mechanism: $A_t \uparrow \rightarrow \theta_t \uparrow; M_t \uparrow \rightarrow \theta_t \downarrow$

Explanation: the mechanism operates through the wage parity channel. For instance, let's consider the case of agricultural technological progress. As agricultural productivity increases, it exerts upward pressure on agricultural wages. In response, labor hours shift towards the agricultural sector to maintain wage parity between the agricultural and manufacturing sectors. A similar rationale applies to manufacturing technological progress.

Proof: Use (12), (15), (21) to rewrite (24) as $w_t = p_t \mu (A_t)^\varepsilon (H_t^A)^{\alpha-1} = \delta (M_t)^\phi$.

Rewrite using the definition of θ_t from (22):

$$p_t \mu (A_t)^\varepsilon (H_t)^{\alpha-1} (\theta_t)^{\alpha-1} = \delta (M_t)^\phi. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Holding p_t, M_t, H_t constant, taking total derivative of (A.2) with respect to A_t :

$$\frac{\partial \theta_t}{\partial A_t} = \frac{\varepsilon \theta_t}{A_t (1-\alpha)} > 0,$$

given $\alpha < 1$.

Holding p_t, A_t, H_t constant, taking total derivative of (A.2) with respect to M_t :

$$\frac{\partial \theta_t}{\partial M_t} = - \frac{\phi \delta (M_t)^{\phi-1}}{p_t \mu (A_t)^\varepsilon (H_t)^{\alpha-1} (1-\alpha) (\theta_t)^{\alpha-2}} < 0,$$

given $\alpha < 1$.

[Mechanism 4: Population growth effect]³⁷

Mechanism: $H_t \uparrow \Rightarrow \theta_t \downarrow$

Explanation: the mechanism operates through the wage parity channel. In this context, agricultural production is characterized by stronger diminishing returns to labor hours compared to the manufacturing sector. Consequently, ceteris paribus, an increase in aggregate labor hours supply exerts a greater downward pressure on agricultural wages relative to manufacturing wages.

To maintain wage parity between the two sectors, households will shift their labor hours from the agricultural sector to the manufacturing sector.

Proof: Holding p_t, A_t, M_t constant, taking total derivative of (A.2) with respect to H_t :

$$\frac{\partial \theta_t}{\partial H_t} = - \frac{\theta_t}{H_t} < 0,$$

given $\alpha < 1$.

³⁷ To be more precise, in our model with labor-leisure choice, mechanism 4 should be called the "labor hours growth effect" instead of the "population growth effect". See Ho (2024) for details on population growth effect.